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Glossary

Acronym/abbreviations	
ACS GCI	American Chemical Society Green Chemistry Institute
BPSA	Bio-Process Systems Alliance
BSI	British Standards Institution
CAS	Chemical Abstracts Service
C(D)MO	Contract (Development and) Manufacturing Organization
DG-ENV	Directorate-General for Environment
DG-JRC	Directorate-General Joint Research Centre
DMP	Data management plan
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EEA	European Environment Agency
EEB	European Environmental Bureau
EFPIA	European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EPLCA	European Platform on Life Cycle Assessment
EU	European Union
EuropaBio	European Association for Bioindustries
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
IHI JU	Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking
ISPE	International Society for Pharmaceutical Engineering

Acronym/abbreviations	
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IQ Consortium	International Consortium for Innovation and Quality in Pharmaceutical Development
LCA	Life cycle assessment
NGO	Non-governmental organization
NIIMBL	National Institute for Innovation in Manufacturing Biopharmaceuticals
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
PEG	Pharmaceutical Environment Group
RTO	Research and Technology Organization
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
SEA	Stakeholder Engagement Activities
TfS	Together for Sustainability
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents an updated Stakeholder Engagement Activities (SEA) Plan, which is a strategic guide that outlines how PHARMECO will identify and engage relevant stakeholders throughout the project. The SEA Plan is essential to ensure that the project remains inclusive, responsive, and aligned with both regulatory expectations and societal needs.

The plan's main goals include:

- Updating the list of stakeholder categories.
- Updating priority stakeholders for early engagement.
- Updating outreach strategies to connect with key stakeholders and build lasting relationships.

Engagement will target a broad community, including industry, academia, regulatory bodies, healthcare professionals, patient groups, and civil society organizations. By stimulating open dialogue and collaboration, PHARMECO aims to accelerate the adoption of sustainable practices across the pharmaceutical value chain.

Particular focus will be given to the regulatory engagement strategy and interaction plan. Active engagement dialogue with regulatory and policy bodies will be crucial to ensure the uptake of PHARMECO results, support the harmonization of sustainability assessment methodologies, and ultimately promote the adoption of new technologies and process improvements stemming from PHARMECO.

The SEA Plan is a living document and will evolve alongside the project. Regular updates will incorporate feedback from stakeholders and project partners to improve engagement approaches and ensure continued alignment with PHARMECO's objectives. Ultimately, this strategy supports effective communication, knowledge sharing, and long-term impact across the healthcare sustainability ecosystem.

1 Description of the deliverable's objective and the content

The PHARMECO Stakeholder Engagement Activities (SEA) Plan is a strategic document designed to guide the consortium's approach to identifying, engaging, and collaborating with relevant stakeholders throughout the project. Its objective is to ensure that stakeholder interaction is proactive, inclusive, and aligned with the project's overarching goals of advancing safe and sustainable pharmaceutical manufacturing.

From the early stages of the project, AbbVie, in collaboration with RISE, is coordinating stakeholders' engagement activities. These include cross-consortium workshops, bilateral meetings, and other interactive formats, which may be organized by different PHARMECO working groups - extending beyond WP9 - depending on the topic at hand. A stakeholder list has been developed collaboratively with all consortium partners, drawing on their networks to identify relevant actors and cooperation opportunities. This will help stimulate early uptake of PHARMECO outcomes. Stakeholders' engagement in PHARMECO will cover strong interactions with Horizon Europe-funded initiatives (e.g., TransPharm) or IHI/IMI projects (such as ENKORE and PREMIER), and other initiatives and fora (including PEG-LCA, NIIMBL, TfS, BioPhorum, the American Chemical Society etc.). These interactions aim to facilitate joint activities, promote synergies in tackling common challenges, and accelerate the uptake of PHARMECO's methodologies, tools, and best practices.

In addition, key external stakeholders, such as manufacturers not being members of PHARMECO, regulatory and competent authorities (linked to Task 9.4), environmental NGOs, civil society actors (including patient groups, healthcare professionals, and consumer organizations), and European standards bodies, will be actively engaged. These interactions will help ensure PHARMECO's work remains responsive to emerging regulatory trends/policy developments and societal expectations, particularly within the evolving landscape of the EU pharmaceutical review.

2 Sections of the deliverables

2.1 SEA strategic goals:

The Stakeholder Engagement Activities (SEA) Plan aims to support PHARMECO's mission through the following strategic goals:

- **Comprehensive stakeholder mapping:** Identify and categorize stakeholder groups according to their relevance, level of influence, and alignment with PHARMECO's objectives.
- **Prioritization of key stakeholders:** Determine which stakeholders to engage first based on their potential impact on the project's core themes of sustainability and pharmaceutical innovation. A Mendelow matrix is used to help with prioritization.
- **Facilitation of dialogue and collaboration:** Establish effective channels for ongoing feedback, knowledge exchange, and collaborative activities across stakeholder groups.
- **Commitment to inclusive and transparent engagement:** Ensure that engagement efforts are equitable, open, and responsive, reflecting the diversity of stakeholder perspectives and evolving needs throughout the project.

2.2 Key Steps in the SEA Process

The PHARMECO Stakeholder Engagement Activities (SEA) Plan adopts a dynamic and structured approach to ensure meaningful and strategic engagement throughout the project lifecycle. The envisioned process includes the following key steps:

- **Stakeholder Identification and Categorization:** New stakeholders will be systematically identified during the project and grouped based on their role, interest, and relevance to PHARMECO's objectives.
- **Prioritization:** Stakeholder groups will be (re-)prioritized during the project according to the project's phase, the relevance to specific tasks, and their potential to influence or benefit from project outcomes.
- **Engagement Execution:** Engagement activities will be conducted through various channels, including the PHARMECO community platform, project events, bilateral meetings, satellite events connected to other meetings and leveraging the networks of consortium partners.
- **Work Package Alignment:** Stakeholders will be mapped to relevant Work Packages and deliverables to ensure targeted and context-specific engagement.
- **Interaction Monitoring:** Stakeholder interactions will be tracked, and contact information will be managed in compliance with GDPR, ensuring ethical and secure data handling practices.
- **Continuous Adaptation:** The SEA plan will remain a living document, regularly updated based on feedback from stakeholders and internal project developments to remain responsive and effective.

2.2.1 Stakeholder identification

The PHARMECO SEA plan includes an evolving list of stakeholders, stored on the internal SharePoint site ([Stakeholder identification.xlsx](#)). This list serves as a foundational reference for engagement activities and is summarized in Table 1. It will guide efforts to connect with the broader PHARMECO community and to populate each category with relevant organizations and individuals.

Preliminary list of Stakeholders:

- Funding bodies (eg IHI);
- Sector organizations (e.g., EFPIA, MedTechEurope, EuropaBio; European Association of Consumer Pharmaceutical Specialties (AESGP), Medicines for Europe);
- Collaborative platforms and networks (e.g., ACS, ACS GCI Pharmaceutical Roundtable, Pharmaceutical Environment Group, Biophorum, NIIMBL, BPSA, IQ Consortium, PEG-LCA or “Pharma LCA”, Together for Sustainability (“TfS”), International Society for Pharmaceutical Engineering (ISPE));
- EU project consortia on environmentally sustainable pharmaceutical practices (TransPharm, SusPharma, Eternal, Impactive, Enviromed, Enkore, Premier etc.) ;
- Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) practitioners (e.g., EPLCA);
- Regulatory and policy-making bodies (e.g., ISO, UNEP, EMA, ECHA, EEA, European Commission, EU Parliament ENVI Committee, and national drug regulatory agencies; Ministry of Health, policy makers);
- Working group on pharmaceuticals and the environment (HMAs);
- Policy and Scientific Advisory Bodies (PEF, DG-ENV, DG-JRC, HTA bodies/Networks);
- Standardization body (BSI);
- Academic institutions and Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs);
- Pharmaceutical and medtech manufacturers not being part of PHARMECO (e.g. IPSEN);
- Supply chain actors (e.g. Lonza);
- Suppliers of chemicals, consumables, and equipment (e.g. Sartorius, Cytiva);
- Environmental NGOs (e.g. European Environmental Bureau (EEB), Healthcare Without Harm (HCWH));
- Patient organisations or initiatives;
- Public health-oriented platforms.

This preliminary list of stakeholders will further grow and mature during the project. Ongoing stakeholder interactions and collaborations are also being logged in an excel-based tool on the internal Sharepoint ([External collaborations - overview.xlsx](#)).

2.2.2 Stakeholder clustering and prioritization

The Mendelow Matrix is a strategic tool used in stakeholder analyses to help prioritizing stakeholders based on two key dimensions:

- **Influence**
How much ability does a stakeholder have to affect the project’s success or decision-making processes. High-power stakeholders can influence funding, approvals, or strategic direction.

- **Interest**

How much the stakeholder cares about or is affected by the project. This could be based on how relevant the project is to their goals, values, or operations.

Stakeholders will be mapped into four quadrants, with engagement activities tailored according to their position. Priority will initially be given to those with high power and/or high interest. However, it is important to recognize that stakeholder priorities may shift over the course of the project.

Figure 1 Mendelow Matrix illustration

Figure 2 PHARMECO's preliminary stakeholders' list grouped into quadrants of Mendelow Matrix

The matrix divides stakeholders into four quadrants:

The results presented below stem from an aggregated score for the complete PHARMECO project.

1. Key Players: High Influence, High Interest (Manage Closely)

- **Regulatory and policy-making bodies** (e.g., ISO, UNEP, EMA, ECHA, EEA, European Commission, EU Parliament ENVI Committee, national ministries of health, and national drug regulatory agencies)
 - These organizations have significant power to shape regulations and policy and a strong interest in sustainable pharmaceutical practices.
- **Policy and Scientific Advisory Bodies** (PEF, DG-ENV, DG-JRC, HTA Networks)
 - These bodies are influential in shaping policy and interested in sustainability and pharmaceutical practices.
- **Sector organizations** (e.g., EFPIA, MedTechEurope, EuropaBio)
 - These organizations represent industries and have high power and vested interest in ensuring their sectors are compliant with sustainability standards and regulations.
- **Manufacturers**
 - Industrial partners in PHARMECO are a representative selection

2. Context Setters: High Influence, Low Interest (Keep Satisfied)

- **Standardization body (e.g. ISO, BSI)**
 - Has power over standard-setting, but its interest may not be as focused on the day-to-day issues related to sustainability.
- **EU project consortia working on more sustainable pharmaceutical practices** (e.g., TransPharm, SusPharma, Eternal, Enkore, Premier etc.)
 - While they hold influence through their funding and EU backing, their primary focus remains on achieving specific project objectives, with broader sustainability in the pharmaceutical sector being a secondary consideration. Nonetheless, by aligning efforts, such as through joint preparation for regulatory discussions, both their impact and strategic influence can be further strengthened.

3. Defenders: Low Influence, High Interest (Keep Informed)

- **Collaborative platforms and networks** (e.g., ACS GCI Pharmaceutical Roundtable, Pharmaceutical Environment Group, Biophorum, NIIMBL, BPSA, IQ Consortium, PEG-LCA)
 - These groups show strong commitment to sustainability and pharmaceutical practices, but they typically have less influence than regulatory bodies or industry organizations. However, by collaborating and aligning their efforts, they can significantly amplify their overall impact.
- **Academic institutions and Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs)**
 - They have a strong interest in sustainability-related research and innovation, but lack the authority to directly drive policy or sector-wide change. Nonetheless, targeted dissemination of PHARMECO results can support the development of human capital, particularly in safe and sustainable pharmaceutical practices.
- **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) practitioners** (e.g., EPLCA)

- They have a keen interest in sustainability but hold limited power in terms of regulatory or industry influence.
- **Environmental NGOs** (e.g., EEB)
 - They have strong interest in sustainable practices but limited power when compared to regulatory bodies or sector organizations.
- **Patient organisations or initiatives**
 - Interested in gaining access to new medicines, not necessarily that pharmaceuticals are sustainable. Their power to influence policy is strong but to influence industry practices is relatively low.

4. Wider audience: Low Influence, Low Interest (Monitor)

- **Suppliers of chemicals, consumables, and equipment**
 - Although involved in the supply chain, they may have low interest in the broader sustainability trends unless there is direct impact on their business model.
- **Supply chain actors**
 - These actors may have limited interest and influence in the sustainability discussions unless their operations are directly impacted.

2.2.3 Stakeholder engagement

The PHARMECO SEA plan is developing a structured workflow to guide stakeholder engagement efforts, which will be implemented once stakeholders have been identified and categorized. This workflow ensures that engagement is strategic, compliant, and aligned with the overall project goals.

Engagement Workflow:

- Prioritize stakeholders based on their level of influence and/or interest to ensure focused and effective engagement.
- Map each stakeholder group to the most relevant PHARMECO Work Packages (WPs) to clarify roles and expected interactions. Some stakeholders may have wide interest in almost all work packages, whereas others may only engage with a single WP.
- Maintain a stakeholder activity log to track engagement history and evolving priorities. Currently, this is managed through an Excel-based document hosted on the internal SharePoint. An alternative may be a CRM database.
- Ensure GDPR compliance by identifying data protection requirements and implementing appropriate safeguards.
- Develop tailored engagement strategies for each stakeholder group, with attention to potential synergies across WPs and relevant external projects.
- Create a timeline for planned engagement activities, prioritizing outreach to high-impact stakeholders.
- Monitor and evaluate engagement efforts, ensuring that activities remain aligned with stakeholder importance and project needs.
- Define documentation protocols, specifying which outputs (e.g., meeting minutes, presentations) should be archived to support transparency and continuity.

Outreach activities to engage with stakeholders will include collaborative workshops, bi-lateral meetings, and targeting scientific conferences. Most likely these will take place under the coordination of WP 9. Where relevant, working groups will be established, and a series of workshops and webinars will be organized to engage with selected stakeholders.

2.3 Strategic alignment, Challenges and continuous improvement

2.3.1 Alignment with Project Goals

The PHARMECO Stakeholder Engagement Activities (SEA) Plan is designed to support PHARMECO's overarching mission of promoting the long-term adoption of innovative, sustainable pharmaceutical development and manufacturing practices. By fostering an informed and engaged community across healthcare, regulatory, academic, and industry sectors, the SEA plan ensures that project outputs—such as research findings, case studies, and training materials—are effectively disseminated through various tailored channels.

2.3.2 Emerging Challenges and Proposed Solutions

1. Identifying actual stakeholders in the different categories

Challenge: Each category needs to be filled with actual organizations, people, contact details etc to engage them.

Proposed solutions: Utilize the PHARMECO community to expand the list and collect suitable contact information for stakeholders.

2. Engaging with Key Stakeholders

Challenge: The stakeholder landscape in PHARMECO spans a broad spectrum of private, public, governmental, regulatory, and non-profit institutions.

Proposed Solutions: Conduct a survey within the PHARMECO community to identify and leverage existing knowledge networks and pinpoint specific stakeholders for targeted engagement.

Involve stakeholders in PHARMECO communication outputs by e.g. consulting them to comment on outputs, inviting them to preface, engage or reflect in round table discussions as part of dedicated events or webinars.

3. Choosing Appropriate Engagement Channels

Challenge: The diversity and geographic distribution of stakeholders require a flexible, well-matched approach to communication.

Proposed Solution: Create a stakeholder-communication matrix to align engagement methods with specific groups. The community survey will also inform participation in key scientific meetings and related events. Stakeholders may be engaged via questionnaires.

4. Tailoring Messaging to Stakeholder Needs

Challenge: Effective engagement requires customized messaging for varied stakeholder profiles.

Proposed Solution: Collaborate with the communications team to produce targeted materials (e.g., handouts, slide decks, briefings, emails) suited to each stakeholder group.

2.3.3 Strategies for Future Improvement

The preliminary SEA Plan has been designed with adaptability as a core principle. Early feedback from internal reviews and stakeholder consultations will inform iterative updates to ensure relevance and responsiveness. The SEA plan will serve as a living document that evolves with stakeholder needs, project developments, and emerging challenges

2.3.4 Regulatory Engagement

PHARMECO aims to galvanise regulatory preparedness and acceptance towards greener pharmaceuticals, by raising awareness through dedicated workshops and developing evidence, guidance and policy briefing documents. This is expected to help decision-making and harmonisation at an EU level and beyond and ultimately facilitate preparedness for sustainable pharmaceutical innovation.

The information and methods used to engage with regulators in PHARMECO will be collected among and scrutinised by the consortium partners. The long-term objective of the data collection is to canvas input and support plans to strengthen necessary capacities to help reduce or eliminate hindrances along the whole life cycle by considering what is needed in terms of regulatory testing. We also want to identify challenges in regulatory frameworks that may hamper the uptake of PHARMECO results.

Our aim is to enable a dialogue with EMA and/or national medical product or drug regulatory agencies around priorities identified by the consortium. These dialogues to share and build knowledge between consortium and regulatory experts, hoping to contribute to forthcoming guidance and policy.

We plan to run workshops with consortia partners, regulators (national and EU) and experts from public institutions on selected issues which are considered priority. Within those workshops, we will engage in discussions about barriers and incentives. The information shared in the workshops and the results thereof will be collated to prepare policy briefings and summaries for the public, so that we can disseminate the knowledge gained and inform future guidance and policy, also beyond the end of the PHARMECO project.

PHARMECO findings are to be communicated to relevant regulatory authorities, particularly when they concern the following topics:

- Identifying regulatory barriers to the uptake of PHARMECO results, such as
 - The variation in requirements across different regulatory jurisdictions (which can become a challenge for pharmaceutical companies who invest in sustainability)
 - The tension between regulatory goals and requirements and new legislative provisions (for instance between requirements for pharmaceutical products and environmental legislation)
- When creating or adapting new production processes, how to address:
 - the lack of knowledge about the new technology or process among regulators,
 - the need to meet requirements for standards and benchmarking
 - the need for (efficient) regulatory filing, also at post-approval level – when changes are needed to a master file
- Identifying incentives to promote sustainability and circular economy – within policy/regulation

Communication Strategy and Activities

Communication to reach relevant authorities will take place through one or several of the following strategies:

1. Direct communication with individual regulatory agencies or their representatives – This will be done in order to establish a dialogue to evaluate whether information obtained within PHARMECO has high regulatory relevance and should be further disseminated.
2. Direct communication with EMA and its representatives – when knowledge has been obtained in dialogue with internal and external partners and deemed to be of high regulatory importance.
3. Scientific articles and commentary papers on matters deemed relevant for regulatory affairs. Such articles could be published in the following scientific journals, Therapeutic Innovation & Regulatory Science (Springer), The AAPS Journal (Springer), Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences (Elsevier), as well as **Regulatory Affairs Journal Pharma (RAJ Pharma), Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology, Pharmaceutical Regulatory Affairs: Open Access, Journal of Pharmaceutical Policy and Practice, etc.**
4. Participation in conferences covering regulatory topics or meetings where regulatory and consortium partners participate.

When communicating to regulatory authorities the previously defined ways were assessed with regards to their challenges and opportunities:

1. **Direct communication with individual local regulatory agencies**
 - Limitations: Resource-intensive, inconsistent responses across agencies, potential for conflicting feedback
 - Opportunities: Tailored engagement, builds direct relationships, addresses country-specific concerns
 - Action: identify potential contacts among national regulatory authorities within PHARMECO team
 - EMA provides a list of contacts of national regulatory agencies for direct communication (<https://www.hma.eu/about-hma/working-groups/eu-innovation-network-eu-in.html#ui-id-5>).
2. **Direct communication with EMA (and other regulatory agencies, such as FDA, other global authorities)**
 - Limitations: Highly formal process, longer response times, requires strong scientific evidence and preparatory work
 - Opportunities: Single point of contact for EU-wide impact, greater harmonization potential, higher credibility if endorsed
 - Action: Contact EMA Regulatory Science to ask for scientific exchange with regulatory experts
 - EMA offers various channels and expert groups to interact with IHI public private partnerships (<https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/other/european->

[medicines-agency-process-engaging-externally-funded-regulatory-sciences-and-process-improvement-research-activities-public-and-animal-health_en.pdf](#)).

- As a guidance, EMA published experiences of staff members and project coordinators about the Involvement of the European Medicines Agency in multi-stakeholder regulatory science research projects (<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2023.1181702>).

3. Scientific and commentary articles

- Limitations: No guarantee of regulatory attention, lengthy publication process, indirect influence
- Opportunities: Establishes scientific credibility, reaches broader audience, creates citable references for future regulatory discussions

4. Participation in regulatory conferences

- Limitations: Infrequent opportunities, limited speaking time subject to invitation to present, competitive attention space, registration fees; e.g. DIA (Drug Information Association conferences)
- Opportunities: Direct networking with decision-makers, real-time feedback, greater visibility and project profile among multiple stakeholders

The WP9 team together with the other work packages will identify information gained within PHARMECO that is especially important for regulatory authorities.

- All reports within PHARMECO should be reviewed to identify information possibly important for regulatory authorities.

Results of PHARMECO with regulatory relevance

The PHARMECO project will, whenever possible, identify main results to be communicated to and discussed with regulators and industry representatives of various regulatory disciplines.

Whenever relevant, for each of the key results, a brief summary and a short list of most relevant questions will be compiled and shared with national regulatory representatives, with EMA and key officials, as well as other potential contacts among the FDA and other regulatory authorities as well as industry regulatory experts. These questions will be framed from a perspective of feasibility, as they will need to meet a need for more information from regulatory stakeholders and be brought forward by the consortium partners when implementing their activities.

3 Conclusion

The updated Stakeholder Engagement Activities (SEA) Plan provides a framework for PHARMECO stakeholder activities throughout the course of the project. It outlines our approach to identifying, prioritizing, and engaging with individuals and organizations that play a role in advancing sustainable pharmaceutical practices. A more comprehensive plan for regulatory engagement has also been included in this SAE update.

Recognizing that stakeholder landscapes and project needs may evolve over time, this plan is designed to be adaptive. Subsequently, it is likely that it will be updated and refined subject to ongoing feedback, internal exchange, and external developments to ensure it adequately reflects what PHARMECO is to achieve in what concerns stakeholder engagement.

Ultimately, meaningful stakeholder engagement is essential to the success of PHARMECO. By fostering collaboration across industry, academia, regulatory and policy bodies, healthcare professionals, and civil society, we aim to create a shared foundation for innovation and long-term impact. Through this inclusive approach, we will aim to support the uptake of sustainable solutions and contribute to the broader and sustainable transformation of the pharmaceutical sector.

4 Annex 1

Table 1: Overview of PHARMECO stakeholder groups and ongoing interactions (30/04/2026)

Groups	Significance	Category	Organization	types	Engagement
Key Players	High power, high interest	Regulatory and policy-making bodies	UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme is the UN agency that coordinates global efforts to address environmental challenges and promote sustainable development.	Ad hoc contribution in scientific advisory board discussions
			EMA ITF	Forum for early dialogue between innovators and regulators to support the development of new medicines and technologies.	
		Sector organizations	EFPIA MQEG/EHSEG	EFPIA's Manufacturing and Quality Expert Group – Environment, Health, and Safety Expert Group, which focuses on improving manufacturing quality and addressing environmental, health, and safety issues in the pharmaceutical industry.	Exploratory discussion on how EFPIA MQEG/EHSEG can support PHARMECO

Groups	Significance	Category	Organization	types	Engagement
Context setters	High power, low interest	EU consortia promoting more sustainable pharmaceutical practices	TransPharm	Horizon Europe projects focused on advancing greener pharmaceutical production, sustainable processes, and enhanced environmental safety throughout the entire medicine lifecycle.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mutual participation in workshops and assemblies to align on activities (avoiding duplication, facilitating synergies). Small overlap in consortium members promotes informal alignment
			SusPharma		
			Impactive		
			Eternal		Exploratory discussions ongoing on how to collaborate, topics of common interest
			PREMIER	IHI project aiming to improve the environmental sustainability of pharmaceuticals through better risk assessment, greener design, and innovative technologies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Topic-specific discussions for collaboration ongoing
		ENKORE			
		Collaborative platforms and networks	ACS-GCI Pharmaceutical Round Table	American Chemical Society – Green Chemistry Institute Pharmaceutical Roundtable brings together industry leaders to promote sustainable practices and green chemistry in the pharmaceutical sector.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exploratory discussions ongoing on how to collaborate In addition, the Director of Sustainable development group is PHARMECO scientific advisory member
			CAS	Chemical Abstract Service is a division of the American Chemical Society that provides comprehensive chemical information, including databases, research tools, and digital resources, to support scientific innovation and discovery.	Areas for potential collaboration have been identified and are being discussed.
			PEG-LCA = Pharma LCA	Pharma LCA consortium is part of the Pharmaceutical Environment Group and brings together industry leaders to improve the environmental sustainability of pharmaceutical companies	

Groups	Significance	Category	Organization	types	Engagement
			BPSA	Bio-Process Systems Alliance industry association promotes the adoption and innovation of single-use technologies in biopharmaceutical manufacturing.	Exploratory discussions ongoing on how to collaborate
			NIIMBLE	National Institute for Innovation in Manufacturing Biopharmaceuticals is a U.S. public-private partnership focused on advancing biopharmaceutical manufacturing innovation, education, and workforce development.	
			TfS	Together for Sustainability is a global industry initiative that promotes sustainable supply chains in the chemical industry through supplier audits, assessments, and collaboration on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) standards.	The TfS General Manager is member of PHARMECO scientific advisory board
			BioPhorum	Industry consortium where biopharmaceutical companies and suppliers collaborate to develop best practices and solutions for manufacturing, regulatory, and operational challenge	Exploratory discussions ongoing on how to collaborate
Defenders	High Interest, Low Power	Academic institutions and Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs)	University of York, Professor Jason Snape		Member of scientific advisory board
			SETU – South East Technological University, Ireland		Discussions ongoing with Department of Pharmacy on how to best include PHARMECO learnings in new course trajectory